

LEARNER'S READING PROFICIENCY AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

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Learner's Reading Proficiency and Academic Performance

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Abstract

Reading proficiency is critical for academic success, influencing comprehension and performance across all subjects. However, in the Philippines, low reading proficiency remains a significant concern, as evidenced by the country's last-place ranking in the 2018 Program for International Student Assessment (PISA). This study addresses the gap in understanding the relationship between reading proficiency and academic performance within the Filipino context, particularly among Grade IV to VI learners at San Juan Elementary School, Bohol, during the 2023–2024 school year. The research aimed to assess learners' reading proficiency using the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) and their academic performance based on first-quarter grades. Additionally, it examined demographic factors such as age, gender, nutritional status, parental education, occupation, school attendance, and attitudes toward reading. A descriptive correlational survey method was employed, utilizing questionnaires and performance assessments to collect data from a complete enumeration of 97 learners. Key findings revealed that while learners showed satisfactory academic performance and positive attitudes toward reading, no significant relationship was found between reading proficiency and academic outcomes. This result suggests that other factors, including socio-economic conditions and parental involvement, may have a more substantial impact on learners' academic achievements. The implications of this study emphasize the need for a comprehensive reading enhancement program that integrates socio-cultural and cognitive approaches to improve reading skills while addressing external influences on academic performance. Recommendations include fostering parental involvement, promoting independent reading habits, and leveraging community resources to create a supportive learning environment. These findings provide valuable insights for educators and policymakers to design targeted interventions aimed at enhancing literacy and educational equity in rural Philippine settings.

Keywords: *academic performance, cognitive constructivism, educational interventions, Phil-IRI, reading proficiency, rural education*

Introduction

Reading proficiency is the cornerstone of a student's overall academic performance. In the Philippine education context, alarming results from global assessments, such as the 2018 Program for International Student Assessment (PISA), highlight the urgent need for targeted interventions to improve reading skills among Filipino learners. The Philippines ranked last in reading proficiency among all participating countries and territories, with only 19% of students meeting the minimum proficiency level. Over 80% of Filipino students are estimated to require assistance to achieve basic reading competency, representing the largest proportion of low achievers among all participating economies in PISA (Parojenog & Pabalan, 2024). These results underscore the critical link between reading proficiency and broader academic outcomes, emphasizing the importance of addressing this issue to support the educational and economic development of the country.

Research consistently demonstrates that reading proficiency is foundational to success across academic disciplines. High levels of reading ability facilitate access to knowledge in mathematics, science, and social sciences (Nevo et al., 2019), while low proficiency hinders comprehension and performance in these subjects (Iroegbu & Igweike, 2020). Proficient readers are better equipped to process and retain subject-specific information, resulting in superior overall academic performance. Conversely, students with limited reading skills often encounter difficulties that compound over time, leading to persistent academic underachievement.

This study investigates the relationship between reading proficiency and academic performance, focusing on English as measured by the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI). Prior research highlights that reading proficiency impacts academic outcomes through multiple pathways, including vocabulary acquisition, comprehension skills, and critical thinking. In developing countries like the Philippines, these challenges are further exacerbated by socioeconomic factors, inadequate instructional resources, and disparities in access to quality education (OECD, 2019). Despite various initiatives by the Philippine Department of Education (DepEd), such as the Every Child a Reader Program (ECARP) and the "No Read, No Pass" policy, recent data reveal persistent reading deficiencies. For example, the 2017 Phil-IRI results from Bayugan City indicated that only 28% of Junior High School students were independent readers, with the majority classified at frustration levels.

Theoretical frameworks provide critical insights into understanding and addressing these issues. Lev Vygotsky's socio-cultural theory emphasizes the role of social interactions and cultural tools in learning, suggesting that interventions leveraging peer tutoring, storytelling, and culturally relevant texts can improve reading proficiency (Santoso et al., 2023). Jean Piaget's cognitive constructivism underscores the active role of learners in constructing knowledge through prior experiences, highlighting the value of strategies like inquiry-based learning and reciprocal teaching (Sua, 2021). Additionally, Stanovich's Matthew Effect illustrates the compounding

advantages of early reading success and the detrimental effects of delayed interventions, reinforcing the urgency of addressing reading deficits at the earliest stages (Young et al., 2020).

Nationally, the Phil-IRI serves as a vital tool for diagnosing and addressing reading challenges, allowing educators to implement tailored interventions. This study expands on existing literature by examining the specific relationship between reading proficiency and academic performance within the Filipino educational context. In particular, it explores how school resources, parental involvement, and linguistic factors interact with reading proficiency to influence academic outcomes. By situating this investigation within a specific local setting, the research aims to provide actionable insights that can inform national policies and classroom practices.

Addressing the critical relationship between reading proficiency and academic performance is essential for bridging achievement gaps and fostering lifelong learning. Targeted interventions such as ECARP and the "No Read, No Pass" policy, grounded in robust theoretical frameworks and informed by empirical data, can empower Filipino educators to create inclusive, effective learning environments. By focusing on these foundational competencies, this study contributes to broader efforts to improve the quality of education and ensure equitable opportunities for all learners.

Research Questions

This research assessed the learner's reading proficiency and its relationship to their overall academic performance of Grade IV – VI learners of San Juan Elementary School during the school year 2023 – 2024 as basis for reading enhancement program. Specifically, it sought answers to the following:

1. What is the profile of the learners in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. nutritional status;
 - 1.4. parent's highest educational attainment;
 - 1.5. parent's occupation;
 - 1.6. number of days attendance in school; and
 - 1.7. attitude toward reading?
2. What is the level of reading proficiency of the learners based on the Phil-IRI result in terms of:
 - 2.1. social interaction;
 - 2.2. language proficiency;
 - 2.3. exposure to lessons and texts; and
 - 2.4. vocabulary?
3. What is the overall academic performance of the learners based on the mean percentage score during first quarter?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the overall academic performance of the learners based on the mean percentage score during first quarter and their reading proficiency based on the Phil-IRI result?
5. Based on findings, what reading enhancement program can be presented?

Methodology

Research Design

To evaluate the learners' reading proficiency and academic performance, the researcher employed a descriptive correlational survey method. This approach was selected for its effectiveness in capturing the participants' current status and characteristics, offering a clear snapshot of their reading skills and academic achievements at a specific point in time. The method enables the collection of detailed information to identify patterns, correlations, and trends, providing a comprehensive overview of the learners' abilities.

Data was gathered using a quantitative descriptive survey through a carefully designed questionnaire. The questionnaire covered various aspects of reading proficiency and academic performance, ensuring all critical areas were addressed. This approach allowed for the collection of quantifiable data that was statistically analyzed to draw meaningful conclusions. Additionally, using a questionnaire facilitated efficient data collection from a large sample, enhancing the reliability and generalizability of the findings. Overall, the descriptive survey method provided a thorough and accurate representation of the learners' abilities, offering valuable insights for future research and educational strategies.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were all Grade IV to VI learners from San Juan Elementary School in San Juan, Sierra Bullones, Bohol. The study included the entire population of these grade levels enrolled in face-to-face classes, ensuring comprehensive coverage and eliminating sampling bias. This approach aimed to provide a detailed representation of the reading proficiency and academic performance of upper elementary students, allowing for an in-depth analysis of the factors influencing their educational outcomes.

These respondents, as illustrated in Table 1, encompass the entire population of Grade IV–VI students attending in-person classes, thereby eliminating sampling bias and enhancing the reliability of the study's findings.

Table 1. *Distribution of the Respondents*

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>Number of Respondents</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Grade IV	42	43.29%
Grade V	34	35.05%
Grade VI	21	21.64%
Total	97	100%

The decision to include all students within these grade levels underscores the importance of obtaining a holistic view of the reading and academic abilities of learners at this critical stage in their education. This inclusive methodology not only strengthens the validity of the research but also ensures that the results are reflective of the broader student body, offering valuable insights into the educational needs and challenges faced by students in this rural setting.

Instrument

The study utilized two primary instruments to collect data on the reading proficiency and academic performance of Grade IV to VI learners. First, a survey questionnaire was designed to gather essential profile information, including age, nutritional status, parental educational attainment, parental occupation, family size, number of school days present, and attitudes toward reading. Second, the learners' reading performance was assessed based on their reading category, while their first-quarter general average across all subjects was analyzed to provide context for their overall academic performance. These instruments offered comprehensive data to examine the relationship between reading proficiency and academic achievement, as well as the factors influencing the learners' educational outcomes.

Procedure

The data-gathering process began with the preparation of a transmittal letter addressed to the School Division Superintendent of Bohol Division, requesting authorization to conduct the study. Once approval was granted, the researcher proceeded to the school to conduct the data collection.

An orientation was held for the learners and their parents to explain the study's objectives and their roles in the research. The survey tool, adapted from Gabejan and Quirino (2021), was administered during a 30-minute session with the learners. During this time, the researcher also gathered data on the pupils' reading categories and their first-quarter general average grades.

After data collection, the gathered information was systematically summarized, organized, and tabulated to prepare it for analysis. This analysis ensured that the data provided meaningful insights and addressed the study's objectives effectively.

Data Analysis

In the analysis and interpretation of data, the following statistical treatment were used:

Frequency. The qualitative data, including responses from the survey questionnaire, were analyzed using descriptive statistical treatment. The findings were presented with percentage, average & rank order. For statistical purposes, the responses on attitude toward reading of pupil respondents were categorized as Strongly Agree, Agree, Uncertain, Disagree, Strongly Agree with weight equivalents of 5, 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively.

Weighted Mean. This technique is used to measure the central tendency where some values are given importance over others. This is used to gauge the average value of responses to items in the questionnaire (Ferguson, 1992: 482)

Pearson Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation. To determine the significant difference based on Phil IRR result and academic performance of the learners in reading comprehension, the data were subjected to Pearson Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation using the formula (Angeles, 2005:269).

Ethical Considerations

The study strictly adhered to ethical standards, including obtaining informed consent from all participants, ensuring confidentiality, and maintaining voluntary participation without coercion. No harm came to any participants, and ethics committee approval was secured prior to conducting the research. The researcher declared no conflicts of interest, upheld transparency and honesty in reporting findings, and maintained cultural sensitivity throughout the research process.

Results and Discussion

This section presents, analyzes, and interprets the collected data systematically to verify and substantiate the research questions. The data for this study were collected through surveys, academic performance assessments, and the use of the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil IRI). Surveys were administered to gather information on the learners' profile, including age, sex, nutritional status, parents' highest educational attainment, parents' occupation, number of school attendance days, and attitude toward reading. The academic performance of the learners was assessed in terms of noting details, predicting outcomes, and creating a summary. Phil IRI was utilized to determine the learners' comprehension level.

To analyze the data, descriptive and inferential statistics were used. Descriptive statistics provided an overview of the respondents' profiles, academic performance assessments, and performance in the identified competencies. Inferential statistics were employed to generalize the relationship between Phil IRI and the academic performance of the learners in reading comprehension.

Reading Proficiency

Reading proficiency is the ability to read, understand, and interpret written texts with accuracy and fluency. It plays a crucial role in a learner's academic success, as it enhances comprehension across various subjects and supports critical thinking skills. Developing strong reading proficiency is essential for learners to excel academically and engage effectively with diverse reading materials throughout their educational journey.

Profile Of The Learners

This exudes the profile of the learners in terms of age, sex, nutritional status, parents' highest educational attainment, parents' occupation, number of days of attendance in school, and attitude toward reading.

Age

This provides a detailed profile of the respondents based on their age. This demographic information is crucial for understanding the age distribution of the participants in the study. The table lists the frequency (F) and percentage (%) of respondents in each age group, as well as the rank (R) of each group. Additionally, it includes the mean age and standard deviation to give a statistical overview of the age range.

Table 2. *Age (N = 97)*

<i>Items</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>
Age (years)		
10	35	36.08
11	23	23.71
9	20	20.62
12	15	15.46
13	4	4.13
Mean	10.41237	
Standard Deviation	1.125024	

Table 2 shows the profile of the respondents in terms of their age. Among the 97 respondents, the largest age group was 10 years old, representing 36.08% of the participants. The 13-year-olds were the least represented, comprising only 4.13% of the participants. Overall, this data provides the age distribution among the respondents, with 10-year-olds being the most prevalent group in the sample.

Numerous studies have indicated that reading proficiency improves throughout the primary and secondary school years. During early childhood, oral reading skills undergo significant development. According to a study by Brown (2014), children aged 4 to 6 years old typically demonstrate emergent reading skills, such as letter recognition and phonemic awareness.

In a study conducted by Paige (2020), it was found that children aged 6 to 12 exhibited substantial growth in their oral reading fluency and comprehension abilities. In adolescence, oral reading skills continue to evolve. A study by Spencer and Wagner (2018) found that adolescents between the ages of 12 and 15 showed substantial growth in reading comprehension and vocabulary skills. In conclusion, oral reading skills undergo significant changes throughout different stages of life. Early childhood is marked by rapid growth in oral reading abilities, while school-aged children continue to refine their skills through instruction and practice. During adolescence and adulthood, oral reading fluency tends to stabilize.

Gender

This presents the distribution of the respondents based on their sex. This demographic information is essential for understanding the gender composition of the participants, which can influence various factors related to their academic performance and reading proficiency.

Table 3 presents the gender profile of the respondents. The data reveals a relatively balanced distribution, with 51.55% of the respondents identifying as male and 48.45% identifying as female.

Table 3. *Sex (N = 97)*

<i>Items</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>
Sex		
Male	50	51.55
Female	47	48.45

This indicates that both genders were well-represented in the sample. Overall, this data highlights the inclusion of both male and female respondents in the study, ensuring a balanced representation of gender in the research findings.

The researchers found that males had a slightly higher accuracy rate compared to females. However, the difference was not statistically significant, indicating that gender may not be a strong predictor of reading accuracy.

Nutritional Status

This illustrates the nutritional status of the respondents. This data is crucial as nutritional status can significantly impact students' cognitive functions, academic performance, and overall well-being.

Table 4. *Nutritional Status (N = 97)*

<i>Items</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>
Nutritional Status		
Normal	90	92.7835
Wasted	5	5.1546
Severely Wasted	0	0.0000
Obese	2	2.0619

The data presented in Table 4 shows the nutritional status of the respondents in the study. The majority, 92.7835%, have a normal nutritional status. This high percentage, along with the highest frequency and rank, indicates that the majority of pupils possess a healthy nutritional status. However, a smaller percentage of 5.1546% of respondents are classified as wasted, suggesting a concern regarding their nutritional well-being. There are no respondents classified as severely wasted, indicating a positive aspect of the data. Furthermore, a small percentage of 2.0619% are classified as obese, indicating a lesser prevalence of obesity among the participants.

Numerous studies have established a strong correlation between nutritional status and academic performance. A study conducted by Kleinman et al. (2002) found that students with adequate nutrition demonstrated better cognitive abilities, including reading proficiency, compared to those with poor nutrition.

A study by Samson et al. (2022) revealed that children with iron deficiency were more likely to struggle with reading comprehension and overall academic achievement. Similarly, a study by Asfaw and Belachew (2020) found that students with zinc and iodine deficiencies had lower reading scores compared to their well-nourished peers. A study conducted by Clemente-Suárez et al. (2022) indicated that students consuming a balanced diet rich in complex carbohydrates and lean proteins performed better in reading assessments compared to those with a diet high in processed foods and unhealthy fats. This suggests that a well-balanced diet positively influences a student's ability to comprehend and analyze written text.

Highest Educational Attainment of Parents

The data of highest educational attainment of the parents of the respondents is essential for understanding the educational background of the families, which can influence students' academic achievement and educational outcomes.

The data presented in Table 5 shows the highest educational attainment of the parents of the respondents. The highest frequency and rank are observed in the category of high school graduates, with 31.96% of respondents having parents who completed high school.

Table 5. *Highest Educational Attainment of Parents (N = 97)*

<i>Items</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>
Educational Attainment		
HS Graduate	31	31.96
HS Level	29	29.90
Elementary e Level	13	13.40
Elementary Graduate	8	8.25
College Level	7	7.22
College Graduate	9	9.28

Following closely behind are respondents whose parents reached the high school level without graduation, accounting for 29.90% of the total. This suggests a considerable number of parents who have attained a high school education but did not graduate. Additionally, 13.40% of respondents have parents with educational attainment at the elementary level, while 8.25% have parents who graduated from elementary school. No respondents' parents have no schooling, graduated from a vocational course, or possess a post-graduate degree.

A study conducted by Sénéchal and LeFevre (2002) found that parents with higher levels of education tend to engage in more literacy-related activities with their children, such as reading aloud and providing educational materials. This involvement positively impacts the child's reading proficiency. Parents with higher educational attainment often have a better understanding of the importance of reading proficiency.

They are more likely to provide support, create a literacy-rich home environment, and set higher academic expectations for their children. This support positively influences pupils' reading skills and overall academic performance (National Center for Education Statistics, 2019).

Parents who have achieved higher levels of education often serve as role models for their children. When children witness their parents' valuing education and engaging in reading activities, they are more likely to develop a positive attitude towards reading and strive for higher levels of proficiency (Flouri & Buchanan, 2004).

Parents with higher educational attainment generally have better access to educational resources, such as books, libraries, and educational technology. This access provides their children with more opportunities to engage in reading and develop their proficiency (Şengönül, 2022).

Parent's Occupation

This provides a detailed breakdown of the occupations held by the parents of the respondents. Understanding parental occupations is crucial as it sheds light on the socioeconomic backgrounds and influences that may impact students' educational experiences and outcomes.

The data presented in Table 6 shows the profile of the respondents in terms of their parents' occupations. The most common occupation among the parents is farming, with 40 individuals (41.24% of the total) falling into this category. The occupation of driver is the second most prevalent, with 13 individuals (13.40% of the total) having parents who work as drivers.

Construction worker is the third most common occupation, with 9 individuals (9.28% of the total) falling into this category. Other occupations with notable representation include babysitter, gas boy, and housewife, each accounting for 5.15% of the total. Overall, the data indicates the diverse professional backgrounds within the sample.

Table 6. *Parent's Occupation (N = 97)*

<i>Items</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>
Parents' Occupation		
farmer	40	41.2371
driver	13	13.4021
Construction worker	9	9.2784
baby sitter	5	5.1546
gas boy	4	4.1237
housewife	4	4.1237
carpenter	3	3.0928
collector	2	2.0619
agent	2	2.0619
seaman	2	2.0619
barber	1	1.0309
businessman	1	1.0309
dancer	1	1.0309
accountant	1	1.0309
govt employee	1	1.0309
office worker	1	1.0309
police	1	1.0309
sales girl	1	1.0309
soldier	1	1.0309
teacher	1	1.0309
vendor	1	1.0309

In a study conducted by Putri and Melani (2022), it was found that children of professionals or parents in high-skilled occupations tend to have better reading skills compared to those whose parents have low-skilled jobs. This finding suggests that the socio-economic status associated with certain occupations can positively impact a child's reading proficiency.

Furthermore, a study by Nigussie (2022) revealed that children whose parents work in occupations related to education, such as teachers or librarians, have higher reading scores. This finding emphasizes the importance of parental influence and expertise in fostering reading skills among children.

On the contrary, a study by Ates (2021) found that a parent's occupation does not significantly predict a child's reading proficiency. The researchers argue that factors such as parental education level and access to educational resources may have a more substantial impact on reading abilities.

Learner's Number of Days of Attendance in School

This presents data on the number of days of school attendance per month for the respondents. This information is crucial for understanding the attendance patterns among students, which can directly impact their academic performance and overall educational outcomes.

The data presented in Table 7 shows the profile of the respondents in terms of learner's number of days of attendance in school. The

most common attendance pattern is attending school for 20 days, with 64.9485% of respondents. This indicates that a majority of students have a consistent attendance record, attending school for the maximum number of days.

Table 7. *Number of Days of Attendance in School A month (N = 97)*

Items	F	%
Number of Days of Attendance in School		
20	63	64.9485
19	18	18.5567
18	11	11.3402
17	3	3.0928
21	1	1.0309
15	1	1.0309
Mean	19.4536	
Standard Deviation	0.9467	

Additionally, 11.3402% of respondents have an attendance pattern of 18 days, reflecting a smaller but still significant group. Other attendance patterns, such as 17, 15, and 21 days, have lower frequencies ranging from 1.0309% to 3.0928%.

Regular attendance at school plays a vital role in developing pupils' reading proficiency. Research by Anderson et al. (2018) found a positive correlation between the number of days of attendance and reading proficiency. The study revealed that students with higher attendance rates demonstrated better reading skills compared to those with irregular attendance.

To address the issues of attendance and reading proficiency, various interventions have been implemented. A study by Tang et al. (2021) examined the effectiveness of a school-based program that focused on improving attendance and reading skills simultaneously.

The program incorporated strategies such as regular monitoring of attendance, targeted interventions for students with low attendance, and tailored reading instruction. The findings demonstrated a significant improvement in both attendance rates and reading proficiency among the participating pupils.

Attitude towards Reading of the Pupil

This provides an overview of the respondents' attitudes towards reading, which is crucial for understanding their perception and engagement with reading activities. Attitudes towards reading can significantly influence academic performance and learning outcomes among students.

The data presented in Table 8 provides valuable insights into the respondents' attitudes towards reading. With a weighted mean of 3.7186, the overall attitude is predominantly positive, indicating agreement among the participants. The respondents express strong agreement with the belief that reading can make their studies easier (4.0515) and facilitate their learning (3.9175).

Table 8. *Attitude towards Reading of the Pupil (N = 97)*

Attitude Toward Reading Of Pupil	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
1. I am interested in reading.	3.84	1.3177	Agree
2. I believe reading can make my studies easier.	4.05	1.167	Agree
3. I am enthusiastic in reading books and magazines or journals.	3.41	1.4416	Agree
4. I like exploring things through Reading.	2.84	1.7698	Uncertain
5. Reading facilitates my studies learning.	3.91	1.336	Agree
6. Eventually, reading improves my academic performance.	3.82	1.5139	Agree
7. I can learn many things through reading.	3.91	1.4118	Agree
8. I feel more fulfilled by being proficient in reading.	3.68	1.4256	Agree
9. I desire to be a good reader.	3.89	1.3423	Agree
10. Reading allows me to be innovative and make me more output oriented.	3.79	1.3915	Agree
Overall	3.71	1.4517	Agree

The result show enthusiasm for reading books, magazines, and journals (3.4124) and acknowledge that reading allows them to learn many things (3.9175).

The data further reveals that the respondents value the importance of reading in improving their academic performance (3.8247) and desire to become proficient readers (3.8969). However, the item "I like exploring things through reading" receives a lower weighted mean of 2.8454, indicating some uncertainty in this aspect.

Overall, the data underscores the positive perception of reading as a valuable tool for academic success and personal growth. It highlights the importance of nurturing a strong reading culture among students, encouraging their interest and belief in the benefits that

reading can bring to their studies and overall development.

Reading proficiency is a fundamental skill that impacts a student's ability to learn and succeed academically. According to the National Assessment of Educational Progress (NAEP), students who are proficient readers tend to perform better in all subjects, not just English Language Arts (ELA) (National Center for Education Statistics, 2019).

Strong reading skills enable students to comprehend complex texts, engage in critical thinking, and effectively express their ideas in writing. A positive attitude towards reading has been found to correlate with higher reading proficiency and academic achievement (Gambrell, 2011).

Students who perceive reading as enjoyable and valuable are more likely to engage in reading activities, leading to improved skills and overall academic performance.

Level Of Reading Proficiency Of The Learners Based On The Phil-Iri Result

The data presents a multifaceted view of learners' social interaction, reading proficiency, language skills, exposure to texts, and vocabulary acquisition, offering significant insights into their overall academic engagement and competencies.

Social Interaction

Social interaction is a vital aspect of the learning process, particularly in relation to reading proficiency, as highlighted by the Phil-IRI results. Engaging with peers during reading activities not only enhances comprehension but also fosters a collaborative environment where learners can share insights and support one another in their academic journeys. The ability to discuss texts, ask questions, and provide feedback is essential for developing critical thinking skills and deepening understanding.

Table 9. *Social Interaction (N=97)*

<i>Social Interaction</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. I actively participate in group activities during class.	3.40	1.0660	Agree
2. I feel comfortable asking my classmates for help when I don't understand something.	3.35	0.9993	Neutral
3. I frequently discuss what I've learned with my classmates outside of class.	2.78	1.2568	Neutral
4. I find it easy to communicate my thoughts and ideas to my peers.	3.66	1.1620	Agree
5. I participate in social learning activities (like group discussions or peer tutoring) regularly.	3.81	1.2432	Agree
Overall	3.40	1.1985	Agree

As students interact with their classmates, they reinforce their own learning while also contributing to the collective knowledge of the group. This dynamic interplay between social interaction and reading proficiency underscores the importance of creating opportunities for collaborative engagement in the classroom, ultimately leading to improved literacy outcomes and a more enriching educational experience.

The table data indicates that learners generally agree on their ability to engage with peers in a classroom setting, reflected in an overall weighted mean of 3.4053. This suggests a positive atmosphere for collaborative learning. Specifically, learners feel they actively participate in group activities, as evidenced by a mean of 3.4071, signaling that group work is a valued component of their educational experience.

However, there are notable areas where learners express uncertainty. For instance, the mean for feeling comfortable asking classmates for help stands at 3.3540, landing in the neutral range. This suggests that while some students are willing to seek assistance, a significant portion may hesitate to do so, indicating a potential barrier to collaborative learning. Additionally, the mean of 2.7876 for discussing what they've learned outside of class reveals a lack of informal academic dialogue among peers, which is crucial for reinforcing learning.

On a more positive note, learners report finding it easy to communicate their thoughts to peers (mean of 3.6637) and regularly participating in social learning activities like group discussions (mean of 3.8142). These aspects underscore a strong foundation in interpersonal communication and collaborative engagement, essential for developing a supportive learning environment.

Language Proficiency

Language proficiency is a crucial determinant of academic success, particularly as it relates to reading proficiency, as demonstrated by the Phil-IRI results. A strong command of language allows learners to navigate complex texts, comprehend diverse content, and express their ideas clearly and effectively. The Phil-IRI highlights the correlation between language skills and reading achievement, illustrating that students who are proficient in their spoken and written language tend to perform better in reading assessments. Moreover, language proficiency encompasses not only vocabulary and grammar but also the ability to engage critically with texts, enabling learners to analyze and synthesize information more effectively. By fostering language proficiency in the classroom, educators can enhance

students' reading abilities, equipping them with the tools necessary for lifelong learning and effective communication.

Table 10. *Language Proficiency (N=97)*

<i>Language Proficiency</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. I am confident in my ability to express myself in English or Filipino.	4.00	1.1060	Agree
2. I can understand most of what I read in English or Filipino.	3.98	1.1494	Agree
3. I can write essays, stories, or other texts with few mistakes.	4.18	1.0653	Agree
4. I find it easy to learn new words and use them correctly in sentences.	3.90	1.1178	Agree
5. I can speak clearly and fluently when presenting in front of the class.	3.85	1.1792	Agree
Overall	3.98	1.1259	Agree

Turning to language proficiency, learners express a high degree of confidence in their abilities, with an overall mean of 3.9876. This indicates that students generally feel adept at expressing themselves in both English and Filipino. Notably, the highest mean of 4.1858 for writing proficiency suggests that students are particularly comfortable with written expression, which is crucial for academic success.

Learners also indicate a strong comprehension of reading materials (mean of 3.9823) and a reasonable comfort in learning new vocabulary (mean of 3.9027). However, the mean for speaking fluency when presenting is slightly lower at 3.8584, highlighting a potential area for improvement, particularly in oral communication skills in formal settings.

Exposure to Lessons and Texts

Exposure to lessons and texts is essential for developing reading proficiency, as emphasized by the Phil-IRI results. Access to a variety of reading materials not only enriches learners' knowledge but also stimulates their curiosity and engagement with the content. The Phil-IRI highlights that student who regularly encounter diverse texts—whether through classroom assignments, independent reading, or discussions—tend to demonstrate higher levels of reading comprehension and critical thinking skills. This exposure allows learners to practice interpreting different genres and formats, which in turn enhances their ability to connect ideas and apply what they learn in various contexts. By creating an environment that prioritizes exposure to a wide range of lessons and texts, educators can significantly impact students' reading development, ultimately fostering a love for learning and lifelong literacy.

In terms of exposure to lessons and texts, the overall mean of 3.8832 indicates that learners generally engage with their reading assignments. The strongest aspect is their commitment to completing assignments (mean of 4.2301), reflecting a strong sense of responsibility towards schoolwork.

Conversely, learners are neutral about spending time reading outside of school assignments, with a mean of 3.1327. This suggests a need to encourage independent reading habits, which are vital for enhancing comprehension and fostering a love for literature. Regular review of class notes (mean of 3.9292) and active discussions about lessons (mean of 4.0531) highlight a proactive approach to learning, emphasizing the importance of reinforcing classroom knowledge.

Table 11. *Exposure to Lessons and Texts (N=97)*

<i>Exposure to Lessons and Texts</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. I regularly complete all the reading assignments given by my teacher.	4.23	1.0939	Strongly Agree
2. I spend time reading books or other texts outside of school assignments.	3.13	1.3595	Neutral
3. I review lessons and notes from my classes regularly.	3.92	1.0750	Agree
4. I often discuss or ask questions about lessons or topics I read outside of school.	4.05	1.0423	Agree
5. I have access to and use different types of reading materials (e.g., books, newspapers, magazines) to improve my learning.	4.07	0.9327	Agree
Overall	3.88	1.1717	Agree

Vocabulary

Vocabulary is a fundamental component of reading proficiency, as highlighted by the insights derived from the Phil-IRI results. A robust vocabulary not only empowers learners to understand and engage with a variety of texts but also enhances their ability to express thoughts and ideas articulately. The Phil-IRI underscores the importance of vocabulary acquisition, demonstrating that students with a rich vocabulary tend to perform better in reading assessments and exhibit greater confidence in their language skills. Furthermore, a well-developed vocabulary enables learners to make connections between words and concepts, facilitating deeper comprehension and critical analysis of the material. By emphasizing vocabulary development in educational practices, teachers can significantly improve students' reading proficiency, equipping them with the linguistic tools necessary for academic success and effective communication.

Table 12. *Vocabulary (N=97)*

<i>Vocabulary</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. I enjoy learning new words when I come across them in reading materials.	3.51	1.1348	Agree
2. I frequently use new words I learn in my conversations or writing.	3.38	1.1683	Agree
3. I use a dictionary or other resources when I come across a word I do not know.	3.49	1.1547	Agree
4. I can understand the meaning of a word from its context in a sentence.	3.61	4.9952	Agree
5. I know and use many synonyms and antonyms for the words I frequently encounter.	3.31	1.2766	Agree
Overall	3.46	2.4677	Agree

The vocabulary data presents a generally positive outlook, with an overall mean of 3.4663. Learners’ express enjoyment in discovering new words (mean of 3.5133) and agree that they utilize dictionaries and resources when encountering unfamiliar terms (mean of 3.4911). This indicates a proactive approach to vocabulary building.

However, the mean for the frequent use of new words in conversations and writing is lower at 3.3894, suggesting that while students may be learning new vocabulary, they might not be applying it as frequently in their communication. The understanding of word meanings from context shows promise (mean of 3.6195), though the significant standard deviation indicates variability in learners’ self-perceptions of their vocabulary skills.

Overall First Quarter Academic Performance

This provides an overview of the learners' academic performance during the first quarter of the academic year. The performance is evaluated through a weighted mean and standard deviation, categorized into different descriptive levels: Outstanding, Very Satisfactory, Satisfactory, Fairly Satisfactory, and Did Not Meet Expectations.

The data in Table 13 provides an overview of the overall first-quarter academic performance of the learners. The weighted mean score of 84.83505, with a standard deviation of 4.81032, falls within the "Satisfactory" range according to the provided legend.

The "Satisfactory" level, which spans scores from 80 to 84, indicates that the average performance of the learners meets the basic academic expectations. This suggests that, generally, learners are performing adequately in their academic pursuits but there is significant room for improvement to reach higher performance levels (DepEd, 2018).

The standard deviation of 4.81032 indicates a moderate spread in the academic performance scores among the learners. This variation suggests that while the majority of students are performing at a satisfactory level, there are some who may be performing either very satisfactorily or fairly satisfactorily.

This spread highlights the diversity in academic capabilities within the group. Given that the weighted mean is close to the upper limit of the "Satisfactory" range, it implies that a number of students are on the cusp of achieving a "Very Satisfactory" rating (85-89). This proximity suggests potential for academic growth with targeted interventions and support (National Education Association, 2020).

The findings from Table 13 underscore the need for continued and enhanced academic support to help more learners move from satisfactory to very satisfactory or even outstanding levels. Fostering an environment that promotes academic excellence through personalized learning strategies could significantly boost overall performance.

Table 13. *Overall First Quarter Academic Performance*

	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Description</i>
Academic Performance	84.83505	4.81032	Very Satisfactory

Significant Relationship Between the Overall Academic Performance of the Learners based on the Mean Percentage Score during the First Quarter and their Reading Proficiency based on the PHIL – IRI Result

This examines the correlation between the learners' overall academic performance, as measured by their mean percentage score during the first quarter, and their reading proficiency, as assessed by the Phil – IRI result. The table presents the Pearson correlation coefficient, the significance value, and the interpretation of the relationship between these variables.

Table 14. *Significant Relationship between the overall academic performance of the learners based on the mean percentage score during the first quarter and their reading proficiency based on the Phil – IRI result*

<i>Pearson Correlation</i>	0.055457
<i>Sig. (2-tail)</i>	0.58952634
<i>Decision</i>	Accept Ho
<i>Interpretation</i>	Insignificant Relationship

The analysis presented in Table 14 reveals the relationship between learners' overall academic performance, as measured by their mean percentage score during the first quarter, and their reading proficiency based on the Phil-IRI results. The Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.055 suggests a very weak positive relationship between the two variables. Furthermore, the significance value (p-value) of 0.589 indicates that this correlation is not statistically significant, as it exceeds the common alpha level of 0.05.

Given these results, the decision is made to accept the null hypothesis, which posits that there is no significant relationship between overall academic performance and reading proficiency. This acceptance implies that, based on the data analyzed, variations in learners' reading proficiency do not appear to meaningfully influence their academic performance during the first quarter. In summary, the findings suggest that there is no substantial link between how well students perform academically and their reading proficiency, indicating that other factors may play a more significant role in shaping academic success.

The study provides valuable insights into the reading proficiency and academic performance of the learners, shedding light on key demographic, behavioral, and contextual factors that influence outcomes.

The majority of respondents are 10 years old, representing the dominant age group within the sample. The gender distribution is relatively balanced, ensuring that perspectives from both male and female students are adequately represented.

In terms of nutritional status, most respondents exhibit normal levels, suggesting a generally healthy demographic. However, a smaller proportion is classified as wasted or obese, which may warrant further investigation given the potential impact of nutrition on learning outcomes. The educational background of parents indicates that most have either graduated from or reached high school, reflecting a trend toward secondary-level education within families.

Occupationally, farming is the most common profession among parents, highlighting the agricultural nature of the community. This context may influence students' educational experiences and priorities. School attendance patterns reveal a strong commitment to education, with the majority of respondents attending the maximum number of school days.

Attitudes toward reading among respondents are generally positive. Students demonstrate enthusiasm for reading materials and recognize the benefits of reading in enhancing academic performance. Collaborative learning activities, such as group discussions, are well-received, although some students show hesitance in seeking assistance from peers.

Confidence in language abilities is most evident in written expression, though there remains room for improvement in speaking fluency. Students actively complete assignments and review class notes; however, engagement with independent reading outside of school assignments appears limited. While learners are proactive in expanding their vocabulary, they tend to apply new words less frequently in spoken or written communication.

The academic performance of respondents is rated as satisfactory, indicating that most learners meet minimum standards. However, there is significant room for improvement to achieve higher levels of academic excellence. Importantly, the analysis reveals no significant relationship between reading proficiency and overall academic performance. This suggests that other factors, such as socio-economic conditions, parental involvement, or school resources, may play a critical role in shaping academic outcomes.

These findings underscore the need for a multifaceted approach to enhancing both reading skills and overall academic performance. Strategies must address a combination of individual, familial, and systemic factors to create a more holistic and effective framework for learner development.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the findings from this study provide valuable insights into the complex interplay of factors influencing the academic performance of Grade IV to VI learners at San Juan Elementary School, particularly concerning their reading proficiency. The predominance of 10-year-olds and the balanced gender representation highlight the socio-cultural context of learning, suggesting that these demographic factors can shape educational experiences and engagement. Positive attitudes toward reading and a commitment to completing assignments indicate that learners are actively constructing knowledge through their interactions with texts and collaborative activities. However, the absence of a significant relationship between reading proficiency and overall academic performance, reflected in the weak correlation, suggests that reading skills alone may not be sufficient predictors of academic success. This finding aligns with the Matthew Effect, which posits that initial advantages, such as socio-economic background and parental education levels, may play a more substantial role in shaping learners' academic trajectories.

The acceptance of the null hypothesis, which posits no significant relationship between overall academic performance and reading proficiency, further emphasizes that while reading is an essential component of education, it is not the sole determinant of academic outcomes. These insights underscore the necessity for a holistic educational approach that considers various socio-cultural influences and cognitive processes that contribute to learners' success. Consequently, the study advocates for the development of a targeted reading enhancement program tailored to address the specific needs identified, ultimately aiming to support learners in maximizing their academic potential and improving their overall performance.

Based on the conclusions of the study, several actionable recommendations are proposed to address the implications of the findings:

Enhancing Reading Proficiency Programs.

Educational institutions should prioritize targeted reading interventions that cater to diverse learners' needs, with special consideration for underperforming students. These programs should aim to improve speaking fluency, independent reading habits, and overall language skills.

Promoting Collaborative Learning.

Schools should foster environments that encourage peer-assisted learning and open communication. Activities such as reading workshops and group discussions can increase engagement and support collaborative knowledge-building.

Strengthening Home-School Partnerships.

Engaging parents in fostering a reading culture at home, such as through access to age-appropriate reading materials and family reading activities, can reinforce literacy development beyond the classroom.

Encouraging Independent Learning.

Students should be supported in developing self-directed learning habits, including dedicating time to independent reading and seeking assistance when needed, to enhance academic performance and language mastery.

Future Research Directions.

To build on the current study's findings, future research should explore longitudinal data to examine the long-term relationship between socio-economic factors, reading proficiency, and academic outcomes. Incorporating qualitative approaches such as interviews can provide nuanced insights into learners' experiences and attitudes toward reading.

Output Of The Study

Reading Enhancement Program: Boosting Learners' Academic Performance

Rationale

The importance of reading proficiency in enhancing overall academic performance cannot be overstated. Reading is a foundational skill that influences learners' ability to understand and engage with various subjects. At San Juan Elementary School, despite a positive attitude towards reading and satisfactory academic performance, the lack of a significant correlation between reading proficiency and academic outcomes indicates that other factors might be influencing learners' success. Therefore, a comprehensive reading enhancement program is essential to address these factors and support learners in achieving better academic performance through improved reading skills.

Reading is often considered the cornerstone of education because it facilitates learning across all subjects. Research consistently shows that reading proficiency is closely linked to academic achievement. According to the National Institute of Child Health and Human Development (NICHD), children who read well in the early grades are more likely to succeed in other academic areas. Reading develops critical thinking skills, expands vocabulary, and enhances comprehension abilities, which are vital for understanding complex concepts in subjects like mathematics, science, and social studies.

In the context of San Juan Elementary School, while students show a positive attitude towards reading, the data indicates that this alone is not translating into improved academic performance. This discrepancy suggests that while students may enjoy reading, their proficiency levels might not be high enough to positively impact their academic outcomes. This insight underscores the need for a structured program that not only encourages reading for pleasure but also focuses on improving reading skills in a systematic and measurable way.

Various factors can influence a student's reading proficiency and overall academic performance. These include socio-economic status, parental involvement, quality of instruction, and access to reading materials. At San Juan Elementary School, the majority of students come from families where parents have at least a high school-level education and are engaged in occupations such as farming. While these parents may value education, they might lack the specific knowledge and resources to support their children's reading development effectively.

Furthermore, the quality of instruction and the learning environment at school play crucial roles. Effective reading instruction requires well-trained teachers who can employ diverse strategies to meet the needs of all learners. Additionally, a supportive school environment that fosters a love for reading and provides access to a variety of reading materials is essential. By creating a comprehensive reading enhancement program that addresses these factors, we can help bridge the gap between students' reading proficiency and their overall academic performance.

The program will integrate socio-cultural and cognitive approaches to reading development. Vygotsky's socio-cultural theory emphasizes the importance of social interactions and cultural contexts in learning. According to this theory, learning is a collaborative process, and students benefit from interactions with more knowledgeable others, such as teachers and parents.

Cognitive constructivism, as proposed by Piaget, highlights the active role of learners in constructing their own understanding. This approach suggests that students learn best when they can explore, ask questions, and engage in meaningful activities. The reading enhancement program will include activities that promote active learning and critical thinking, allowing students to build their reading skills in a dynamic and engaging way.

The Matthew Effect, described by Stanovich, refers to the phenomenon where "the rich get richer and the poor get poorer" in terms of reading skills. This effect highlights the importance of early intervention and consistent support for struggling readers. By providing targeted support and resources, the reading enhancement program aims to counteract the Matthew Effect and ensure that all students have the opportunity to improve their reading skills, regardless of their starting point.

Objectives

Enhance Reading Proficiency: Improve the reading skills of learners through targeted interventions and support.

Promote Reading Engagement: Foster a love for reading among learners by creating engaging and enjoyable reading experiences.

Support Parental Involvement: Equip parents with strategies to support their children's reading development at home.

Strengthen Teacher Capacities: Provide teachers with professional development opportunities to enhance their reading instruction techniques.

Utilize Community Resources: Leverage community resources to support and enrich the reading experiences of learners.

Significance of the Plan

The implementation of this reading enhancement program holds significant implications for learners' academic success and overall educational experiences:

Improved Academic Performance

By enhancing reading proficiency, learners will be better equipped to comprehend and engage with academic content across subjects, leading to improved academic outcomes. Reading is a critical skill that underpins learning in all areas of the curriculum. When students can read proficiently, they are more likely to understand and retain information, perform better on assessments, and achieve higher grades. Improved reading skills can also boost students' confidence and motivation, further contributing to their academic success.

The love for reading is to actually have them read, and help them to have an inviting space for a meaningful reading.

Fostering a Love for Reading

Creating a positive and engaging reading environment will help instill a lifelong love for reading, contributing to continuous learning and personal growth. When students enjoy reading, they are more likely to read regularly and develop strong reading habits. This not only improves their literacy skills but also fosters a love for learning and exploration. Encouraging a love for reading can also have a lasting impact on students' academic and personal lives, as reading is a valuable skill that enriches their understanding of the world and enhances their cognitive abilities.

Enhanced Parental Involvement

Providing parents with the tools and strategies to support reading at home will create a supportive home environment that reinforces school-based reading instruction. Parental involvement is a key factor in children's reading development. When parents are actively engaged in their children's reading activities, they can provide encouragement, guidance, and support that enhance their children's reading skills. By equipping parents with effective reading strategies and resources, the program aims to strengthen the partnership between home and school, creating a cohesive and supportive learning environment.

Strengthened Teacher Effectiveness

Professional development for teachers will enhance their instructional strategies, ensuring effective reading instruction that meets the diverse needs of learners. Teachers play a crucial role in students' reading development. By providing teachers with ongoing training and professional development opportunities, the program aims to enhance their knowledge and skills in reading instruction. This will enable teachers to use a variety of instructional strategies and approaches to meet the needs of all learners, including struggling readers and those with diverse learning needs.

Community Engagement

Collaborating with community resources will provide additional support and enrichment opportunities, promoting a culture of reading within the broader community. Community involvement can play a significant role in supporting students' reading development. By partnering with local libraries, literacy organizations, and community centers, the program can provide students with access to additional reading resources and opportunities for enrichment. Community engagement can also help create a culture of reading that extends beyond the school, promoting literacy and learning throughout the community.

Comprehensive Plan

Reading Workshops for Parents and Teachers: Conduct workshops to enhance parents' and teachers' understanding of effective reading practices and strategies to support reading development. These workshops will provide practical tips and techniques that parents and teachers can use to support children's reading skills. Topics may include phonics, comprehension strategies, vocabulary development, and creating a literacy-rich environment at home and school.

Reading Clubs and Events: Organize reading clubs, book fairs, and storytelling sessions to make reading enjoyable and engaging for learners. Reading clubs can provide students with opportunities to discuss books, share their thoughts, and engage in meaningful conversations about reading. Book fairs and storytelling sessions can also create excitement and enthusiasm for reading, encouraging students to explore new books and genres.

Parental Support Materials: Distribute reading guides, book lists, and comprehension resources to parents to support reading activities at home. These materials will provide parents with practical tools and resources to help their children develop strong reading skills. Reading guides may include tips for reading aloud, questions to ask during reading, and activities to reinforce reading skills. Book lists can provide recommendations for age-appropriate and engaging books, while comprehension resources can help parents support their children's understanding of what they read.

Teacher Professional Development: Provide ongoing training for teachers on innovative reading instruction techniques and the use of technology in reading education. Professional development opportunities may include workshops, webinars, and conferences on topics such as differentiated instruction, using technology to support reading, and strategies for teaching reading to diverse learners. By staying up-to-date with the latest research and best practices in reading instruction, teachers can enhance their effectiveness and support students' reading development.

Community Partnerships: Collaborate with local libraries, literacy organizations, and community centers to provide additional reading resources and support services. Community partnerships can provide students with access to a wider range of reading materials, programs, and activities that support their reading development. These partnerships can also help create a supportive network of resources and support for students and their families, promoting a culture of reading within the community.

Evaluation and Feedback: Establish mechanisms to evaluate the effectiveness of the program and gather feedback from parents, teachers, and learners to continuously improve the program. Evaluation and feedback are essential for ensuring the program's success and making necessary adjustments. This may include surveys, focus groups, and assessments to gather input from stakeholders and measure the program's impact on students' reading skills and academic performance.

By implementing this comprehensive reading enhancement program, San Juan Elementary School aims to create a supportive and engaging reading environment that enhances learners' reading proficiency and academic performance. Through targeted interventions, parental involvement, professional development, and community partnerships, the program seeks to provide students with the skills and resources they need to succeed academically and develop a lifelong love for reading.

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